

Corruption In The
Public Sector Of
Ghana: The
Motivating Factors

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ABSTRACT

The study examines corruption in the public sector of Ghana; the motivating factors. Descriptive research approach was deployed and a multi-stage sampling technique was used to select 140 internal auditors and 50 external auditors from Ghana Audit Services across four regions. However, 153 questionnaires were received and analysed making a response rate of 80.5%. Low integrity of public officials, failure to implement audit recommendation and failure to severely punish the perpetrators were the most serious fraud motivating factors. It was also observed that the corruption incidence in Ghana is high and that, combating corruption in Ghana would take a long time to succeed. This stems from the fact that political will to fight corruption was identified as the most effective strategy to combat corruption yet it was seen as the most serious challenge in combating corruption in the country. It, therefore, recommends that the government should show and demonstrate strong political will to fight corruption. Also, Anti-Corruption institutions which includes Ghana Audit Service, should be given support including legal backing to prosecute corrupt officials. Key officials occupying critical positions in the public institutions should be members of professional institutions in the country where integrity forms part of their code of ethics.

Key Words: Corruption, Motivating Factors, Integrity, Effective Strategies, Corporate Governance, Economic growth, Combating, Anti-corruption institutions

1. INTRODUCTION

The ultimate economic goal of every government is to mobilize resources in order to provide citizens with access to basic modern facilities and services required for them to function as productive members of the society. This requires the government to efficiently and effectively deploy the limited resources to productive economic activities that would promote healthy standard of living. However, in recent times, these limited resources are wasted through corruption. The World Bank (1997) defines corruption as the abuse of public office for private gains. Public office is abused for private gain when an official accepts edicts or extorts a bribe. It is also abused when private agents actively offer bribes to circumvent public policies and processes for competitive advantage and profit. Public office can also be abused for personal benefit even if no bribery occurs through patronage and nepotism, the thereof state assets or the diversion of state resources.

In contributing to corruption incidence, Ekiyor (2005) contextualized corruption in the public sector as unlawful use of official power or influence by an official of the government either to enrich himself or further his course and/or any other person at the expense of the public, in contravention of his oath of office and/or contrary to the conventions or laws that are in force. It is clear from these definitions that, corruption is the use of one's power and authority to unlawfully control resources for private benefits. It can happen in many ways including bribery, fraud and nepotism, unlawfully gratuity favour, illegal political contribution, influence

peddling etc. Fraud is a key scheme use to commit corrupt activities. Even though corruption is a broader concept which includes fraud, this paper considers fraud and corruption as one phenomenon

Corruption is a common and anti-development phenomenon in both developing and developed countries. Majority (58%) of Africans believe that corruption is on the rise over the past year (Carolie, 2015). Association of Certified Fraud Examiners (2016) also posit that corruption is a global problem and that no country is free from corruption. It affects organizations of all sizes, types, and, industries, regardless of whether their operations cross jurisdictional lines. It has a devastating effect on the economic development of a country. It leads to poor quality service, injustice, low standard of living, unemployment and lost of trust in the political system (Tanzi, 1998 ; Iroghama 2011 and Ngwube & Okoli, 2013). Corruption retards development and breed insecurity in the country. It is very obvious to say that, no country can successfully achieve its goals if corruption remains high in the governance system. It is in the best interest for any government to institute anti-corruption laws and strictly enforce them to reduce incidences of corruption. It requires strong political will to fight corruption and every one must be part of the process especially those with powers and authorities.

Ghana in its quest to fight corruption and to ensure transparency and accountability, the government over the past years operationalized some Acts and Action Plan to deal with this harmful phenomenon. These include Internal Audit Act (Act 658, 2003), Financial Administration Act (Act 654, 2003), Procurement Act (Act 664, 2003), National Anti-Corruption Action Plan (2012-2021) etc. However, it appears that the fight against corruption in Ghana is getting worse with recent corruption cases including SADA Scandal, GRA-Subah Inforsolutions Ghana Limited (Gh¢144million), Wayome Scandal (Gh¢51million) A research by Coralie (2015) reveale that the rate of corruption in Africa has increased over the past years with South Africa (83%), Ghana(76%) and Nigeria (76) among the top three countries with high corruption perception index. This evidence suggests that there is more to just formulating laws to deal with corruption. In order to establish a framework to prevent, control and manage risk of corruption, it is very important to understand factors that push or pull people to engage in fraudulent activities (Thanasak, 2013). This paper, therefore, seeks to uncover what motivates people to engage in corrupt practices in Ghana.

1.1 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study seeks to achieve the following objectives.

- To examine specific factors that motivate people to engage in corrupt practices
- To find out the effective strategies to combat corruption
- To identify challenges in the course of combating corruption

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

This section reviews empirical studies on corruption. Due to its harmful effects on the economic development of a nation, corruption received more attention from researchers in recent times (Gee & Button, 2015). The focus areas include corruption and governance system, the motivating factors, strategies in dealing with corruption, challenges in the fight against corruption in the public sector.

2.2 CORRUPTION AND GOVERNANCE SYSTEM

In order to ensure effective and efficient use of economic resource in the public sector, there should be strong corporate governance system. The corporate governance system specifies the distribution of rights and responsibilities among different participants in the establishment such as the boards, managers, shareholders and other stakeholders and spells out the rules and procedures for making decisions on corporate affairs. This will provide the structure through which the public institutions' objectives are set and means of attaining those objectives and monitoring performance. Belay (2007) provides elements of good governance system in the public sector as transparency at all levels of the organizational structure; accountable to people concern; effective, efficient and economical use of resources; making information accessible to the stakeholders in the organization and equitable treatment of stakeholders. Incorporating these key elements into a governance system will eliminate corruption or reduce its occurrence. This evidence suggests how government can play a key role to combat corruption in the public sector as there is inverse relationship between effective governance system and corruption (Jenny & Erlinda ,2006 and Ngwube & Okoli, 2013). Corruption flourishes when internal controls system is weak as corrupters would take the advantage of the loopholes in the system to act (Mackevičius & Giriūnas,2013).

2.3 CORRUPTION AND FRAUD MOTIVATING FACTORS

Corruption does not happen in a vacuum but rather, there are factors that pull or push people to engage in corrupt practices. In an attempt to understand fraud motivating factors, many theories were proposed. These include Fraud Triangle Theory (Cressey, 1950), Fraud Diamond Theory (Wolfe & Hermanson, 2004) and Fraud Pentagon Model (Abayomi, 2016). Fraud Triangle Theory states that for fraud to occur, Pressure, Opportunity and Rationalization must be present. Pressure is what causes a person to commit fraud which include financial problem, living beyond means, more personal debt, high family dependency. Opportunity refers to the ability to commit fraud and this stems from weak internal control system, collision and one's position and authority. The research by Mawanza (2014) reveals that work place fraud in Zimbabwe is mainly driven by Pressure and Opportunity factor . Rationalization is to justify fraud act because others are doing it or it is necessary to survive (Abdullahi & Mansor 2015). Wolfe & Hermanson (2004) added Capability to Cressey (1950) fraud motivating factors. Abayomi (2016) argued that personal ethics is also important in assessing fraud motivating factors. However, these theories did not demonstrate much on how the interactions of these variables could lead to fraud. On the basis of this, the researcher proposed Institutional-Personal Factor (Pull-Push Factor) theory of

fraud. This theory combine Fraud Triangle Theory, Diamond Fraud Theory and Fraud Pentagon Model. Figure 1 below provides the details.

Figure 1: Institutional-Personal Factor (Pull-Push Factor) Theory of Fraud

The personal (push) factors are Integrity, Ability and Pressure. These variables are unique to an individual and they push him or her towards committing fraud. One thing is to commit fraud and another thing is to conceal it (Mackevičius . & Giriūnas,2013). A fraudster would always wish to escape punishment. Therefore, the person committing the fraud should be brave and intelligent enough to engage in fraudulent activities and this is the ability factor in the theory. Integrity refers to the quality of being honest, fair, truthfulness and having strong moral principles. The institution provides opportunities for one to commit fraud through weak governance system. Treisman (2000) posits that the incidence of corruption is high in countries with weak political institutions. This confirms the need to have strong institutions that would ensure the practice of good corporate governance. The pressure is when a person is facing financial difficulties or leaving beyond means.

From Figure 1, the Red text indicates the presence of fraud while Green text shows absence of fraud. A person with a high level of personal integrity with low ability and limited pressure and opportunity to commit fraud is most likely to behave honestly. Similarly, an individual with less personal integrity with high ability, when placed in situations with increasing pressure and given the opportunity, is most likely to commit fraud (Hall & Singleton, 2005). The most important variable in this theory is integrity. It is the only variable that has inverse relationship with other variables. This implies that when public officials uphold high level of integrity in all their dealings, the tendency of committing fraud would be low even if the corporate governance system is weak. Such officials would even contribute to make the system strong and effective. If top management and other officials with power and authority have high integrity, they would not collude to circumvent the controls.

2.4 EFFECTS OF CORRUPTION ON NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT

Corruption by nature is anti-development phenomenon that retards economic growth. Sarkar & Hasan (2001) were of the view that the presence of corruption inflicts substantial economic costs on an economy and on the other side, it reduces both the volume and efficiency of investment. High and rising corruption in a country

would increase income inequality and poverty, create unequal distribution of assets ownership and unequal access to education (Gupta, Davoodi & Alonso-Terme, 1998). According to Shao, Ch. Ivanov, Podobnik & Stanley (2007), there is negative correlation between corruption and long term economic growth. Negin, Abd Rashid & Nikopour (2010) in their contribution to this subject matter observed that, corruption and poverty go together, with bidirectional causality. Aina (2014), however, observed that, there is no empirical evidence to suggest that corruption is responsible for poverty but agreed that corruption fuels poverty. That is, corruption has indirect effect on poverty. It is clear from these evidences that, corruption distorts resource allocation and government performance thereby affecting economic growth. It can trigger economic and political instability in any country. Therefore, it is in the best interest of all stakeholders most especially those with powers and authorities to combat corruption in order to foster economic growth.

2.5 STRATEGIES IN DEALING WITH CORRUPTION

Combating corruption in any institution should begin with embracing good corporate governance system. Once there is strong and effective governance system, there would be no or limited opportunities for the personal factors to push individual to commit fraud. There would be incentive to engage in corrupt activities if offenders are not detected and punished (Quah, 2001). Severe punishment of offenders would serve as deterrence for others. Siddiquee (2010) also observed that the most important and powerful institutional mechanism for fighting corruption in Malaysia is Anti-Corruption Agency (ACA). To combat corruption, the Anti-fraud institutions should understand the elements of fraud motivating factors (Abdullahi & Mansor, 2015). Hess & Dunfee (2000) recommend effective auditing system and good protection for whistleblowers as part of strategies to combat corruption. Just auditing is not enough but there should be strong political will on the part of government to implement the audit recommendations if not, the auditing would serve no purpose. Iyanda (2012) observed that corruption is a culture in Nigeria and the only way to fight it is to follow due process and fair play. This position was advanced by Ademu (2013) who argue that the best way to eradicate corruption in the public sector is to adopt Singapore Model. This model provides that sectional heads should be held responsible for any act of corruption in the unit if detected and that, government should have political will to fight corruption. Encouraging the culture of discipline and integrity would help eliminate or reduce corruption in the public sector.

3. METHODOLOGY

As stated earlier on, the main purpose of this study was to look at corruption in the public sector; the motivating factors. Once the study does not intend to manipulate any variable, descriptive research approach is deemed appropriate.

The target population of the study were the Internal Auditors in the various institutions and the External Auditors from Ghana Audit Service. In the view of the researcher, these participants are constantly in contact with those responsible for the management of public resources and therefore, would be in good position to provide relevant, reliable and accurate data for this study.

A multiple stage sampling technique was used. Firstly, the researcher used the regions in Ghana as clusters. After this, a simple random sampling was used to select four (4) regions out of the ten (10) regions. Regional capitals in these selected regions were used for the study. The reason for this selection was based on the fact that the head offices of all the public sector institutions in the regions are located in the regional capitals. Finally, purposive sampling technique was used to select 140 internal auditors and 50 external auditors, making a sample size of 190 respondents.

The main instrument used for data collection was structured questionnaire with most questionnaire items being closed-ended using Likert Scale. The researcher personally contacted some of the respondents while others were reached through email and support from past students. SPSS was used to process the data collected for analysis and discussion.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section is devoted for results and discussion of the findings. It covers respondents' perception of corruption incidence in Ghana, factors that push and pull people to engage in corrupt practices, Examples of corrupt practices, strategies in combating corruption and challenges in fight against corruption.

4.1 PERCEPTION OF CORRUPTION INCIDENCE IN GHANA

This paper sought the views of the respondents concerning the rate of corruption in the public sector of Ghana. Likert-type of scale was used to measure the perception of the respondents ranging from Very High (5) to very Low (1). Table 1 depicts the results

Table 1: Perception of Corruption Incidence in Ghana

Rating of Corruption in Ghana		Internal Auditor	External Auditor	Total
Low	Count	8	6	14
	% within corruption	57.1%	42.9%	100.0%
	% within Profession	7.5%	12.8%	9.2%
Undecided	Count	4	6	10
	% within corruption	40.0%	60.0%	100.0%
	% within Profession	3.8%	12.8%	6.5%
High	Count	31	9	40
	% within corruption	77.5%	22.5%	100.0%
	% within Profession	29.2%	19.1%	26.1%
Very High	Count	63	26	89
	% within corruption	70.8%	29.2%	100.0%
	% within Profession	59.4%	55.3%	58.2%

$$\chi^2 (3, N=153) = 6.362, P = .059$$

Statistical evidence from table 1 reveals that there was no significant difference between External and Internal Auditors regarding their views on the rate of corruption incidence in Ghana, $\chi^2 (3, N=153) = 6.362, P = .059$. It was observed that majority (89) representing 58.2% of the respondents rated corruption incidence in Ghana as very high. A good number of them (40, 26.1%) also rated it as high, while insignificant number (14) representing 9.2% rated it low. This evidence suggests that the corruption incidence in Ghana is high. This study confirms the work of Coralie (2015) who reported that corruption in Africa for the past years has increased with Ghana among the top three countries. The most serious incidences of corruption the respondents mentioned include; inflating contract value and poor execution of contracts, bribery, procurement fraud, inflating overheads expenses especially fuel consumption and assets mismanagement.

4.2 FRAUD MOTIVATING FACTORS

This section of the paper looks at fraud motivating factors. The respondents were asked to what extent do they disagree or agree with the fraud motivating factors the researcher suggested on a five-point Likert-Scale from Strongly Disagree (1) to Strongly Agree (5). See Table 2 for details

Table 2: Fraud Motivating Factors

	Factors	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	Mean	F	Sig.
WCGSPS	Between Groups	.526	1	.526	4.3312	3.130	.079
	Within Groups	25.357	151	.168			
	Total	25.882	152				
AUPCCF	Between Groups	.447	1	.447	4.784	1.261	.263
	Within Groups	53.566	151	.355			
	Total	54.013	152				
FSPP	Between Groups	3.725	1	3.725	4.830	31.497	.000
	Within Groups	17.857	151	.118			
	Total	21.582	152				
LIPO	Between Groups	.035	1	.035	4.9346	.572	.451
	Within Groups	9.311	151	.062			
	Total	9.346	152				
PICR	Between Groups	18.223	1	18.223	3.673	21.259	.000
	Within Groups	129.437	151	.857			
	Total	147.660	152				
HFP	Between Groups	27.160	1	27.160	3.399	21.414	.000
	Within Groups	191.520	151	1.268			
	Total	218.680	152				
LBM	Between Groups	3.743	1	3.743	4.510	12.155	.001
	Within Groups	46.493	151	.308			
	Total	50.235	152				
IND	Between Groups	6.448	1	6.448	4.3725	33.212	.000
	Within Groups	29.317	151	.194			
	Total	35.765	152				
PP	Between Groups	2.109	1	2.109	4.261	11.610	.001
	Within Groups	27.433	151	.182			
	Total	29.542	152				
GRD	Between Groups	.259	1	.259	4.725	1.293	.257

	Within Groups	30.212	151	.200			
	Total	30.471	152				
FEAR	Between Groups	.018	1	.018	4.856	.142	.707
	Within Groups	18.819	151	.125			
	Total	18.837	152				
RoF	Between Groups	.111	1	.111	3.725	.178	.674
	Within Groups	94.359	151	.625			
	Total	94.471	152				

WCGSPS= Weak Corporate governance System in the Public Sector

AUPCCF= Ability to use one's Position to Commit and Conceal Fraud

FSPP= Failing to Severely Punish Perpetrators

LIPO= Low Integrity of Public Official

PICR= Performing Incompatible or Conflicting Roles

HFP= High Financial Pressure

LBM= Living Beyond Means

IND = Indiscipline

PP= Political Pressure

FEAR= Failure to Enforce Audit Recommendation

RoF= Rationalization of Fraud

It was evident from Table 2 that, low integrity of public officials which falls under personal factors, was the most serious fraud motivating factor considered by the respondents (Mean=4.9346, $F=.572$, $P=.451$). Top management with high integrity would design strong internal controls and ensure that employees comply with them. Such management would not do anything to impair the controls. People with high integrity can control themselves not to use fraudulent means to come out from their financial difficulties and other external forces. It was also observed that failure to implement audit recommendation (Mean=4.856, $F=.142$, $P=.707$) and failure to severely punish the perpetrators (Mean, 4.830, $F=31.497$, $P=.000$) were the other key factors that trigger corruption. If the officials know that they would be severely punished for fraudulent act if they are exposed by auditors, would behave honestly. In the same way, if audit recommendations are not implemented, the essence of auditing would be defeated and the moral effect auditing has in preventing corruption would be lost paving way for dishonest officials to continue with their corrupt practices.

The respondents unanimously strongly agreed that ability to use one's position to commit and conceal fraud was another major fraud motivating factor, (Mean, 4.784, $F=1.261$, $P=.263$). This falls under ability in Institutional -Personal (Push-Push factor) theory of fraud. This paper argue that a person with knowledge and experience on the job has ability to commit and conceal fraud than the one with less knowledge and experience. The evidence also suggests that people engage in corrupt practices because of greediness (Mean, 4.725,

$F=1.293, P=.257$) and living beyond means (Mean, 4.510, $F=12.510, P=.001$) but not due to financial pressure (Mean, 3.399, $F=21.414, P=.000$). One can argue that even without pressure, greedy officials would take the advantage of the weakness in the corporate governance system to act fraudulently. Greediness can be attributed to lack of integrity. It can be deduced that people who engage in corrupt practices generally lack integrity. The institution may create opportunity but people with high integrity would not take this advantage to engage in corrupt practices but would rather help to strengthen the controls and ensure their compliance.

Fraud does not take place in a vacuum. The environment of the institution can either promote or prevent fraud act. In the same way, individual factors can push them to engage in fraud practice or restrain them from committing fraud. When institution provides a conducive environment for fraud through weak governance system combine with individual push factors, the incidence of corruption would be high.

4.3 STRATEGIES TO COMBAT FRAUD AND CORRUPTION

Corruption is a deadly anti-development phenomenon and no environment should be created for it to flourish. Therefore, this papers examines the strategies that are effective in combating fraud and corruption. Details are presented in Table 3 below.

Table 3: Strategies to Combat Fraud and Corruption

Strategies	VE		E		SHE		LE		NE	
	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%
Strong and effective corporate governance system and responsibility	125	81.7	28	18.3	0	0	0	0	0	0
Effective anti fraud laws and regulations and ensure strict compliance	120	78.4	33	21.6	0	0	0	0	0	0
There should be range of new criminal penalties for fraud and other wrongful acts	108	70.6	37	24.2	0	0	8	5.2	0	0
Effective Accounting Oversight Board	93	60.8	60	39.2	0	0	0	0	0	0
Auditor independence by creating more separation between firm's attestation and non-auditing	84	54.9	69	45.1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Political will to fight corruption	145	94.8	8	5.2	0	0	0	0	0	0
Uphold high personal integrity	133	86.9	20	13.1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Fair remuneration of workers	52	34.0	51	33.3	50	32.7	0	0	0	0
Issuer and Management Disclosure	73	47.7	72	47.1	8	5.2	0	0	0	0

Very Effective(VE), Effective (E), Somehow Effective (SE), Less Effective (LE) and Not Effective (NE)

Statistical evidence from Table 3 reveals that, political will to fight corruption is the most effective way to combat corruption in the public sector as majority (145) representing 94.8% of the respondents rated it as very effective strategy. This is in line with the thinking of Ademu (2013) who argue that the best way to eradicate corruption in the public is to hold sectional heads responsible for any act of corruption their units and that government should have political will to fight corruption. A government with a political will to fight would resource anti-corruption institutions including giving them legal backing to prosecute offenders. Public officials upholding high personal integrity in discharging their duties would reduce if not eliminate corruption as 86.9%

of the respondents believe it as a very effective strategies to combat corruption. Strong and effective corporate governance system and responsibility was among the top three strategies that can effectively combat corruption. Effective anti fraud laws and regulations and ensuring strict compliance can effectively combat corruption as 78.4% of the respondents rated it as very effective. This corroborates the work of Siddiquee (2010) who observed that the most important and powerful institutional mechanism for fighting corruption is Anti-Corruption Agency. This agency should be given the necessary support to effectively fight corruption. Without support, these institutions cannot function very well. It was also clear from the study that implementing a range of new criminal penalties for fraud and other wrongful act is also a very effective strategy with 70.6% of the respondents supporting it. Statistical evidence also suggests that fair remuneration of workers was the least strategy in fighting corruption with only 34.0% rating as very effective. This could be attributed to the fact that, financial pressure was not seen as a serious factor motivating people to engage in fraudulent activities. It was established in this paper that people can engage in fraudulent act due to greediness.

4.4 CHALLENGES ASSOCIATED WITH COMBATING CORRUPTION

The paper seeks to find out from the respondents the challenges associated with fighting corruption in the country. The researcher provided options for them to tick as many as possible. Figure 1 below depicts the results.

Figure1: Challenges associated with Combating Corruption

PI= Political interference;

IAPCO= Independent auditors protecting corrupt officials

CATOE= Collusion among top officials and other employees

PF= Poor filling and documentation

DESAEP= Difficulties in getting sufficient and appropriate evidence for prosecution

Empirical evidence from Figure 1 shows that, majority (148) representing 96.7% of the respondents believe that political interference (PI) hinders the fight against corruptions. They were of the view that the party in power

protects corrupt officials who are loyal to the party in order not to lose them. The next serious challenge was collusion among top officials and other employees with 135 (88.2%) respondents affirming it. Collusion among top officials undermines the contribution of effective internal control systems. No matter how strong the controls are top officials with low integrity can collude in order to circumvent the controls to perpetrate fraud. It was also observed that getting sufficient and appropriate evidence for prosecution is another challenge in combating corruption as a good number (100) representing 65.4% of the respondents confirmed it as a challenge. Other challenges including poor filing and documentation (96, 62.7%) and independent auditors protecting corrupt officials (40, 26.1%).

5. CONCLUSION

The corruption incidence in Ghana is high and the evidence suggests that combating corruption in Ghana would take a long time to succeed. This stems from the fact that political will to fight corruption is described as the most effective strategy to combat corruption. On contrary, political interference was seen as a serious challenge to combating corruption in Ghana. This means that past and present government did not demonstrate any political will to combat corruption but rather protecting their corrupt officials.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

On the basis of the conclusion drawn, the paper suggests the following recommendation:

- Government should show and demonstrate strong political will to fight corruption. This should be a deliberate policy on how to fight corruption and enforce its implementation. In implementing it, no one should be given preferential treatment.
- Anti-Corruption institutions which includes Ghana Audit Service, should be given support including legal backing to prosecute corrupt officials
- There should strong and effective corporate governance system at each level of government.
- Competent Internal Auditors should be employed and given the necessary support to monitor other internal controls.
- Since top management are responsible for designing and implement strong controls, they should be members of professional institutions in the country. These institutions would instill the culture of professionalism and integrity in their members and also monitor their conduct including corrupt act. These professional institutions have important roles to play in combating corruption.

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